

Brain Tumor Detection Using Convolution Neural Network

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Detecting brain tumor is an important aspect in medical diagnosis, as it greatly impacts patient outcomes. Convolutional neural network has done extraordinary improvements in image recognition methods. This study introduces a new CNN approach to improve the precision and efficiency of detecting Brain Tumor. The proposed method has a lot of stages that uses of machine learning. Initially, the images undergo a preprocessing step to standardize and normalize them. Then, a CNN architecture is developed and trained on a large dataset comprising both tumor and non-tumor MRI scans. The model is trained extensively with annotated data to learn distinctive features that differentiate between tumor and healthy brain tissues.

Keywords—CNN, MRI, features.

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

Brain tumor detection is crucial for early finding of brain disease and disorders, as it greatly affects patient outcomes. Precise finding of tumors is required for effective medical diagnosis. However, normally people often rely on manual intervention by doctors and it is also time-consuming and selective to errors. To address this problem, there is a need for automated and improved techniques to assist medical professionals.

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are powerful and great tools for image analysis, including medical image analysis. Their ability to train and implement unique complex problems from large datasets holds significant potential for improving tumor detection. This research paper gives a new and good approach that utilizes CNNs to accurately identify and segment brain tumors in MRI scans. By training a CNN model on an supreme dataset of augmented MRI images, the goal is the model to learn different features that differentiate between tumor and healthy brain tissues.

This study contributes by developing and evaluating using CNNs. Extensive experiments show the precision and efficiency of the approach in accurately detecting brain tumors. The results have significant improvements for medical diagnostics, providing healthcare professionals with a reliable, great and automated tool to aid in timely decision-making for patient care.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Overview of Literature

The existing body of research using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) demonstrates significant advancements in the field. A lot of studies have concentrated on using CNNs to automate and improve the precision of brain tumor detection from MRI images. Researchers have explored various CNN architectures to capture complex spatial patterns and hierarchical representations in brain images. These architectures incorporate convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers to learn discriminative features for tumor identification efficiently. Additionally, researchers have investigated preprocessing techniques to enhance CNN performance. Skull stripping, intensity normalization, and image registration have been employed to improve image quality and remove non-tumor regions, thereby enabling more accurate tumor segmentation.

Training strategies for CNN models have also been improved, with machine learning being widely adopted. Pre-trained CNN models, originally trained on large-scale image classification tasks, are fine-tuned on brain tumor datasets to leverage their learned knowledge. Data augmentation techniques, including rotation, flipping, and zooming, have been used to address data scarcity issues and improve the generalization of CNN models. Finding of CNN-based brain tumor detection systems has been used in various metrics such as precision, sensitivity, specificity, and AUC-ROC. Comparative studies have demonstrated the superiority of CNN models over traditional machine learning algorithms and highlighted their potential for real-world clinical applications. The importance of large annotated datasets for training CNN models has been emphasized, and publicly available benchmark datasets like BRATS have facilitated benchmarking and result reproducibility.

Overall, the study literature on CNN based brain tumor detection shows great methods in leveraging machine learning methods for precise and automated tumor identification. The advancements have the grip to improve diagnostic capabilities and assist healthcare professionals in making timely and informed decisions.

B. Technology

The project is built using Python, Python is a high-level programming language. The front end is made from Flask web framework, HTML, CSS, and JS to implement a website fetching images. The Flask module is used to fetch images from the user input on a website. The backend is made from Python, Tensorflow, Keras, and OpenCV. Tensorflow consists of a wide range of machine learning models.. Keras is a Python module built on top of TensorFlow. It is mainly used in implementing neural networks. In our project, we imported other modules like BatchNormalization, Conv2D, and MaxPooling2D from the Keras module. Open CV is a image processing python module.

III. DESIGN

Building a model using the CNN in Tensorflow & Keras. Using brain MRI image data found on Kaggle. You can find it here. The dataset contains 2 folders: yes and no, which include 253 images. Folder yes had 155 pictures that are tumorous and folder no had 98 pictures that are non-tumorous.

A. Data Augmentation

Data augmentation is a technique used in CNNs to expand the training dataset by applying various transformations to the original images. Using data augmentation, we will augment our dataset of images. First, fetch the MRI pictures from the OS directory and pass them into the ImageDataGenerator function from the Keras, preprocessing module to provide knowledge such as rotation angle, width_shift_range, height_shift_range, etc. Then save the generated samples into the directory. Before data augmentation, the dataset consisted of 155 positive and 98 negative samples. After data augmentation, the dataset now consists of 1085 positive and 980 negative examples, resulting in 2065 example images. Data augmentation also resolves data imbalances.

B. Data preprocessing

First, we saved the image into our directory, and the image was converted into a grayscale image using the OpenCV Python library. The grayscale image is blurred using techniques such as Gaussian blur. The blurred image is processed by thresholding the image and passing it through erosions and dilations filters. The new image was obtained. We will find the boundaries present in the new image to obtain the largest contour. The cropped image was returned.

Figure 1 – Image after preprocessing

C. Model Architecture

- First, the image size is defined which was (240,240,3) in our case to build our model.

- Zero padding is done to re-size the image to the nearest power of 2. It can also reduce noise in the corners of the picture.
- The padded image is passed through 32 filters of CNN to remove even more noise.
- Batch normalization is done so to increase model speed and reduce overfitting. The image is processed through Batch Normalization to extract further features. Then it is processed through RLEU Linear Unit to reduce if there is any non-linearity in the image. ReLU is the non-linear activation function.
- Then the image is processed through Maxpooling2D twice to obtain the pooled image. This is done so to reduce overfitting, reduce the computational load time, and improve average pooling.
- After applying the filters the image will be in the multidimensional array, to reduce it to a 2-dimensional array, Flatten() and Dense() functions are used to convert the image into a 2D image. The final image is returned.

Figure 2 – Model Neural Network

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The model was saved using a pickle object, the pickle object is opened when the app is started. The best CNN model is extracted from the object to perform fit and prediction methods. The formulas for calculating accuracy are given below:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TrueNegatives + TruePositive}{TruePositive + FalsePositive + TrueNegative + FalseNegative}$$

Another way to calculate accuracy is:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of correct predictions}}{\text{Total number of predictions}}$$

The model had trained for 22 epochs and these are the loss

& accuracy plots:

Figure 3: Accuracy Plot

Figure 4: Loss Plot

The performance table provides the end results of the research.

Performance Table:

	Validation set	Test set
Accuracy	91%	89%
F1 score	0.91	0.88

The formula for the standard F1-score is:

$$F_1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{recall}} + \frac{1}{\text{precision}}} = 2 \times \frac{\text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$$

$$= \frac{\text{tp}}{\text{tp} + \frac{1}{2}(\text{fp} + \text{fn})}$$

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